

AvengER: Ensembling and Fine-Tuning LLMs for SELECT Prompts in Entity Resolution

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Abstract. Link Discovery plays a vital role in enhancing connections between data sources within the Linked Open Data Cloud. A key aspect of this process is Entity Resolution (ER), which focuses on identifying owl:sameAs relationships between different entity descriptions representing the same real-world object. Recent works on ER have investigated the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for Entity Matching, showing promising results. In the simplest case, a pair of entities is given as input to an LLM, asking whether these entities match or not. A recent approach introduced SELECT prompts, which include the query entity along with multiple candidates generated by a Blocking method. However, this increases the complexity of the questions posed to LLMs, while being susceptible to position bias among the presented candidates. To address these issues, we introduce AvengER, a novel approach to SELECT prompts for LLM-based Matching that effectively handles both unsupervised and supervised settings. For the former, we introduce a hybrid approach that utilizes an ensemble of open-source medium-size models (8b) and also selectively leverages (in just 12% of the cases) an external larger-size Judge (32b), thus balancing high accuracy with computational efficiency. For the latter, we use a dataset containing data from multiple domains to fine-tune a medium-size model so that it surpasses both its pre-trained version and pre-trained large-size models (GPT-3.5).

Keywords: LLMs · Entity Matching · Model ensembles · Fine-tuning

1 Introduction

Entity Resolution (ER) facilitates the integration of independent data sources by identifying their *duplicates* or *matches*, i.e., different entity descriptions that refer to the same real-world object [2]. ER constitutes a crucial and challenging task for realizing the vision of Linked Data, facilitating a diverse set of applications, from common data analytics tasks to advanced question answering [3, 4]. The Linked Open Data (LOD) Cloud³ forms a central part of the Semantic Web,

³ <https://lod-cloud.net/#about>

Do these two entity descriptions refer to the same real-world entity?	
(1) [COL] name [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H [COL] description [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H/ Belt Drive System/ 33-1/3 and 45 RPM Speeds/ Servo Speed Control/ Supplied Moving Magnet Phono Cartridge/ Bonded Diamond Stylus/ Static Balance Tonearm/ Pitch Control	
(2) [COL] name [VAL] Sony Picture Station Digital Photo Printer - DPPFP95	
LLM Response: No	MATCH Prompt

Select an entity description from the following candidates that refers to the same real-world entity as the given entity description. Answer with the corresponding entity description number surrounded by "[]" or "[0]" if there is none.	
Given entity record: [COL] name [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H [COL] description [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H/ Belt Drive System/ 33-1/3 and 45 RPM Speeds/ Servo Speed Control/ Supplied Moving Magnet Phono Cartridge/ Bonded Diamond Stylus/ Static Balance Tonearm/ Pitch Control	
Candidate records:	
[1] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-29F Analog Record Turntable - DP29F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive	
[2] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PS-LX350H Belt-Drive Turntable	
[3] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PSLX300USB USB Record Turntable [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 119.72	
[4] [COL] name [VAL] Sony Picture Station Digital Photo Printer - DPPFP95	
[5] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-300F Analog Record Turntable - DP300F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 328.99	
LLM Response: [2]	SELECT Prompt

Fig. 1: Prompts for different tasks. The first decides for a pair of entities, the second selects from a given list of choices.

expanding from 570 datasets in 2014 to 1,573 in 2024. However, its interconnectivity remains limited, with only 17,882 links recorded as of December 2024. On average, each dataset connects to just 11 others, which accounts for roughly 1% of all possible links. To improve this connectivity, Link Discovery automates the identification of relationships between entity descriptions across datasets.

A typical end-to-end ER pipeline consists of two steps: Blocking and Matching [3]. The first step identifies candidate pairs that are likely to match, while the second applies a more precise method to determine which pairs are genuine matches. The last few years, Blocking has been studied with supervised settings [1] and Matching has been dominated by approaches that combine pre-trained transformer models with Deep Learning, such as DITTO [6] and Unicorn [16], while more recent studies leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) [12, 15, 18]. Most of the latter approaches feed LLMs with *MATCH prompts*, which ask whether two particular entities are matching [12, 15]. Yet, these prompts are impractical and time-consuming in the context of end-to-end ER pipelines, where Blocking typically yields k candidates per entity [11, 9]. To address this, *SELECT prompts* are proposed in [18], including all Blocking candidates in a single prompt. This transforms Matching from a binary decision (“Yes / No”) into a “select which of the following” response, as shown in Figure 1. A major challenge with SELECT prompts is position bias, where LLM responses depend on the duplicate’s position among k candidates [18]. This is indirectly addressed through a post-Blocking refinement step that reduces candidates using k intermediate MATCH prompts, trading efficiency for effectiveness.

In this work, we propose *AvengER*, a comprehensive approach that enhances the SELECT prompts by minimizing the impact of position bias in a more efficient and effective way. Rather than relying on intermediate MATCH prompts,

AvengER applies post-Blocking refinement through *reciprocity*: two entities are candidates only if each one is among the top- k most similar entities for the other. This strategy significantly reduces the number of candidates per entity, while conveying a minor decrease in Blocking effectiveness. To further enhance Matching performance, *AvengER* employs multiple LLMs, combining their outputs through diverse *voting strategies*: internal ones, where the ensemble of models decides independently, external ones, where a separate model acts as a judge, and hybrid ones, where a judge decides in case the ensemble is not certain. Despite the higher run-times, our thorough experimental analysis demonstrates that *AvengER*’s combination of reciprocity and voting schemes offers a better balance between effectiveness and efficiency under the *unsupervised* settings.

Under the *supervised* settings, where annotated data are available, *AvengER* fine-tunes medium-sized models, improving the performance of SELECT prompts to such an extent that position bias is mitigated without the need to reduce the candidate pairs generated by Blocking. Their performance is also significantly higher than their pre-trained version and than large-sized models.

Overall, we make the following contributions:

- We introduce *AvengER*, a novel LLM-based Matching approach that leverages SELECT prompts, handling both unsupervised and supervised settings.
- Under unsupervised settings, *AvengER* suggests a categorization of existing Post-Blocking strategies and employs a new one that drastically reduces candidate pairs based on reciprocity.
- *AvengER* further improves ER performance under unsupervised settings through voting strategies that combine the results of an ensemble of LLMs.
- Under the supervised settings, *AvengER* fine-tunes medium-sized LLMs to maximize the robustness of SELECT prompts and their mitigate position bias, significantly outperforming their pre-trained version and large-sized LLMs.
- We demonstrate the superiority of *AvengER* compared to baselines and state-of-the-art through an extensive experimental study that uses several real-world datasets.

2 Related Work

We organize the recent works on LLMs for ER in the following categories:

Blocking. The state-of-the-art Blocking methods detect the k most likely matches per query entity [9, 11]. Higher values for k typically increase Blocking recall, at the cost of more candidate pairs and, thus, lower Blocking precision. For this reason, the goal of Blocking is to achieve a good balance between recall and precision. To improve this balance, a hybrid post-Blocking refinement strategy is proposed in [18]: it constructs “MATCH” prompts, which return a “yes / no” answer, and “COMPARE” prompts, which choose the most likely match among two candidates for the query entity at hand. Both prompts are applied to a

Fig. 2: The phases and steps of *AvengER*. Fine-Tuning the model is optional (dashed).

medium-sized model, yielding a ranking of options, which then produce the top- N results, where N is a parameter defined by experimentation. The overhead, though, is much larger than traditional Blocking methods, due to the large number of prompts.

Matching. In Matching we have two distinct categories. In Prompt Engineering, typically, a matching prompt consists of three parts [12]: (a) the task description, which describes Matching as the task of determining whether two entity descriptions refer to the same real-world object; (b) a serialization of the entity descriptions of the given candidate pair; (c) optionally, a set of examples, with each one comprising a candidate pair along with its label (match / non-match). These examples yield *few-shot prompts*, whereas their absence yields *zero-shot prompts*. A thorough investigation of variants of both types is presented in [12]. Prompts containing multiple candidates, instead of a single pair, have been investigated in [18].

Fine-Tuning improves the accuracy of a pre-trained LLM on a specific task by updating its parameters on a new dataset [15]. To this end, the LLM is partially retrained using $\langle \text{input}, \text{output} \rangle$ pairs of representative examples of the desired behavior. A thorough study of the impact of this approach on Matching is presented in [15], which emphasizes the generalization across different domains and the impact of training dataset size. A related approach leverages an LLM to generate explanations and then uses these explanations to fine-tune a PLM (FlanT5-base) to perform the matching [17]. Augmentation strategies to increase the amount of training data have also been considered in [19]. Finally, a fine-tuned model using transfer learning can outperform competitors on zero-shot prompts, while reducing inference time by nearly 4,000 times [22].

3 *AvengER* Components

AvengER consists of two main phases, as shown in Figure 2: Candidate Generation and Matching. The former receives as input a pair of data sources, D_1 and D_2 , and returns as output a set of candidate pairs C , such that Blocking recall and precision are maximized. The second phase receives as input the set of candidate pairs C and returns as output a set of matching pairs M , such that ER recall and precision are maximized. Putting it all together, Algorithm 1 presents the main steps of *AvengER* in pseudo-code. Initially, Blocking is performed and

Algorithm 1 *AvengER*'s end-to-end algorithm.

Require: Query entity q , blocking parameter k , post-blocking refinement parameter N , List of models $models$, collection C

Ensure: Final result $result$

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1:  $candidates \leftarrow blocking(q, k, C)$ 
2:  $candidates \leftarrow post\_blocking\_refinement(q, N, candidates)$ 
3:  $prompt \leftarrow construct\_prompt(q, candidates)$ 
4:  $responses \leftarrow \{\}$ 
5: for each  $model$  in  $models$  do
6:    $responses.add(model.inference(prompt))$ 
7: end for
8:  $result \leftarrow voting(responses)$ 

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refined with the post-Blocking approaches presented in Section 3.1 (Lines 1-2). Then, the prompt is constructed by one of the methods discussed in Section 3.2 (Line 3). The prompt is then passed to Model Inference and then, the responses of the individual models are aggregated (Lines 4-7). Finally, a voting scheme is optionally applied (Line 8). Fine-Tuning, if needed, is a process done offline. Below, we explain their functionality in more detail.

3.1 Candidate Generation

Based on [21], *AvengER* applies a state-of-the-art approach to *Standard Blocking*: it uses S-GTR-T5 to vectorize the serialized entity descriptions and then performs approximate nearest neighbor (NN) search with FAISS⁴ in order to efficiently detect the k most similar descriptions per query entity. S-GTR-T5, which extends GTR [10], is a dual encoder that transforms two pieces of text into two dense vectors. GTR models are built on top of T5 [13], an encoder-decoder model that aims to unify all natural language processing tasks under a single model. They also use the Siamese architecture in [14] for efficient and scalable similarity computations.

Typically, Standard Blocking achieves high recall by generating large sets of candidates that involve repeated and non-matching pairs. This results in low Blocking precision. *AvengER* aims to significantly increase Blocking precision at an insignificant cost in recall through the *Post-Blocking Refinement* step. We suggest a taxonomy of existing and new Post-Blocking strategies, that involves three categories for removing repeated and non-matching pairs:

1. **Ranking:** Assuming that every candidate pair is associated with a matching probability, this strategy simply retains the top- N weighted ones; $N (\gg k)$ sets the maximum number of candidates forwarded to Matching, with its actual value set arbitrarily or according to experimental results. *AvengER* conveys two implementations of this strategy: (i) *COS-ST5* uses the cosine similarity scores between embedding vectors already computed during the

⁴ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/faiss>

- NN search of Standard Blocking. (ii) *COMPARE prompts* involve a query entity along with two of the candidates determined by Standard Blocking, requesting the LLM to rank them from the most to the least similar one [18]. This requires $\binom{k}{2}$ invocations per query entity.
2. **Filtering:** This strategy reduces the number of candidates by pruning the pairs that are more unlikely to be matching. *AvengER* conveys two implementations of this strategy: (i) *Reciprocal pruning* performs NN search for the entity descriptions of both D_1 and D_2 , retaining only the pairs (e_i, e_j) , where e_j is among the top- k candidates of e_i and vice versa for e_i . (ii) *MATCH prompts* assess whether every candidate pair involves duplicate descriptions and prunes those that do not [18]. In both cases, the number of candidates differs among the input entities (there might even be cases with empty lists).
 3. **Hybrid:** This strategy combines the other two, retaining only the top- N weighted candidate pairs generated by Filtering. In the case of *MATCH prompts*, this can be accomplished by first requesting that each pair is assigned a matching probability and then ranking the results accordingly.

3.2 Matching

We present the steps of *AvengER*'s Matching in the order they are applied.

Prompt Construction. We now elaborate on the structure of the prompt used as a first step for *AvengER*'s Matching.

Basic Prompt. The standard prompt for EM, first introduced in [12], consists of two core parts. The first one is the *task description*, which specifies that the goal is to find entities that refer to the same real-world entity. This can be formulated as a "Yes/No" question [12, 15, 18]. When given a pair of entities, the prompt can be formulated as "select which of the following" [18].

The second part pertains to the *entity serialization*. Many approaches have been proposed in the literature, but since an entity consists of triples $\langle \text{subject}, \text{predicate}, \text{object} \rangle$, two are the most common options: the *schema-agnostic* one, where only the objects are concatenated into a single sentence [21], and the *schema-aware* one, where the format is $[\text{COL}]\text{predicate}[\text{VAL}]\text{object}$ [6].

We propose extensions for both parts. In the task description, we focus exclusively on *SELECT prompts*, asking LLMs not only to respond to the query, but also to explain their choice. As experimentally shown in Section 4, this leads to a better performance for some models. We also tried another prompt, where we instructed the model to provide a *confidence* estimation for its choice [20]. Instead of a numeric score, we requested a qualitative response among three options: "Certain", "Moderately-certain" and "Uncertain". Note that in any prompt type, the model can respond that it cannot decide, returning the special answer of [0], which indicates that none of the choices is correct. Both prompts can be found in Figures 5 and 6.

For the entity serialization part, we also examine a semantically richer description that is generated through a pre-processing step that provides the LLM

with the serialized entity and requests a summary in natural language. This is demonstrated in Figure 7. Then, inside the EM prompt, we replace the entity serializations with their summary.

In-context Learning. Adding examples before the main question in prompts helps LLMs to better understand the given task [12, 15]. This has been widely exploited in EM literature, but only for MATCH prompts [18]. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first to explore enriching SELECT prompts with examples in an experimental setting, yielding few-shot EM SELECT prompts. We have selected examples randomly, but there is room to investigate more advanced strategies in the future.

Model Inference. For model inference, some works [12, 18, 5] use pre-trained models, particularly the large ones like GPT-3.5. In other works [12, 15], Fine-Tuning shows to improve the performance of a model. For example, in [12] a fine-tuned GPT-3.5 can outperform a pre-trained GPT-4 on certain benchmarks.

In our task, the problem is transformed from binary classification to selecting the index position, which is heavily dependent on the order of the choices within the prompt. To enhance robustness, we introduce prompt permutations to train the model on variations in choice positions, thus reducing position bias.

Voting. All existing works on LLM-based EM, rely on individual LLMs. In this work, we go beyond them by considering ensembles of LLMs. We actually examine multiple strategies for combining the individual decisions of multiple LLMs. These strategies depend on whether the ensemble determines the vote internally or relies on an external judge to make the final decision.

Internal Vote. We introduce the following internal voting strategies:

- *Majority-Vote.* Each model produces one answer, and the most-voted answer is selected. If no majority is reached, the ensemble yields an *indecisive* vote, similar to [0], when the true answer is not among the options.
- *Weighted-Vote.* Each model’s contribution is weighted based on its performance, with *precomputed* global weights derived from metrics like F1-score (see Section 4). The answer with the highest total weight is selected.
- *Confidence-Vote.* Instead of relying on pre-computed weights, this method assigns weights *dynamically* based on the confidence scores generated by each model’s response. By utilizing a confidence prompt, we derive a unique weight for each model per response. This approach adapts to the context of each query, making it more flexible than static weight assignments. We introduce 3 certainty levels, {Certain, Moderately Certain, Uncertain}, which are evaluated to {0.5, 0.75, 1}, resembling Shannon Entropy.
- *Aggregated Majority-Vote.* This approach involves asking each model N times with different permutations of answer choices in each iteration. Instead of relying on m votes from the original models, this process generates $m \times N$ votes. By aggregating these votes, the ensemble improves the overall robustness, as models demonstrating consistent predictions across iterations have a stronger contribution to the final decision.

	D ₁	D ₂	D ₃	D ₄	D ₅	D ₆	D ₇	D ₈
Dat ₁	Abt	Amz	ACM	IMDb	IMDb	TMDb	Wmt	DBLP
Dat ₂	Buy	GPr.	DBLP	TMDb	TVDB	TVDB	Amz	Scholar
R ₁	1,076	1,354	2,294	5,118	5,118	6,056	2,554	2,516
R ₂	1,076	3,039	2,616	6,056	7,810	7,810	22,074	61,353
P ₁	3	4	4	13	13	30	6	4
P ₂	3	4	4	30	9	9	6	4
D	1,076	1,104	2,224	1,968	1,072	1,095	853	2,308

Table 1: Statistics of the real ER datasets used in the experiments, showing the number of resources ($|R_x|$), distinct predicates ($|P_x|$) and duplicates ($|D|$).

Regarding computational differences, notice that Weighted-vote requires training, whereas Confidence-vote does not; for inference, there is no significant difference in cost. Notice also that Confidence-Vote expresses each model’s confidence qualitatively, while Aggregated Majority-Vote quantifies it.

External Vote. We introduce the following external voting strategies:

- *Judge-vote.* The idea of using an LLM as a judge for evaluating other LLMs on open-ended questions was proposed in [23]. We apply this by merging individual LLM responses into a prompt for the judge model, since each LLM accompanies its response with an explanation regarding the given answer. Due to the large prompt size, the judge model requires an LLM with a large context window, involving more parameters and resources.
- *Hybrid-vote.* To mitigate the extra cost of asking a heavier judge model, we also propose a hybrid voting strategy. In this approach, we assume that the top-1 answer accumulates a score Σ , which depends on the internal voting strategy (majority, weighted, etc). We also define a threshold $\theta \in [0, 1]$. If $\Sigma < \theta$, we invoke a Judge model to make a decision. In this way, we save computational cost, by reducing the cases where the Judge model is invoked.

4 Evaluation

4.1 Experimental Setup

Datasets. We use 8 real-world ER datasets that are widely used in the literature [8, 18]. Our approach assumes that each entity comprises a set of $\langle \text{predicate}, \text{object} \rangle$ pairs, which are then serialized into a single textual description. This approach accommodates both relational and Knowledge Graph data. For example, the movie datasets (D4, D5, D6) stem from the MovieGraphBenchmark⁵, using URIs as predicates. Table 1 shows the statistics of these datasets. Following [18], we sampled 300 annotated resources per dataset and 100 non-annotated entities (when possible) for testing. For training, we sampled again 300 labeled and 100 unseen pairs, which were also used in the Weighted-vote. For in-context learning, we used 1 positive example, where the answer was among the provided options,

⁵ <https://github.com/ScaDS/MovieGraphBenchmark>

and 1 negative example, where the answer was not included in the provided options. Both examples were randomly selected.

Models. We used five open-source LLMs: Llama-3.1:8b, Mistral-v0.3:7b, Orca-2:7b, Qwen-2.5:32b⁶, and Flan-T5-XL⁷. These models were selected to ensure comparability with state-of-the-art works while leveraging their specific strengths. Llama and Mistral were used in almost all experiments and were also utilized in [18], facilitating direct comparisons. Orca was included in the ensemble due to its strong reasoning capabilities [7], which are beneficial for decision-making in multiple-choice settings. Qwen, being a larger model, served as a Judge in External Voting, while Flan was used for MATCH prompts in ComEM, as in [18]. For brevity, we omit their parameters in subsequent references.

Baseline LLM-based EM. The top performing LLM-based approach to EM is presented in [18]. It utilizes Sparkly [11] for Blocking and Hybrid for Post-Blocking Refinement. The constructed prompt is based on the basic SELECT format with no examples and the model is a pre-trained GPT-3.5-turbo-0613.

Evaluation Metrics. For all experiments, we report F-Measure (F1). For the Voting Strategies, we also report Precision and Recall, whereas for Blocking, we also report the corresponding Blocking Precision, Recall and F1. We also report the average response size in characters.

Settings. For Standard Blocking, we used S-GTR-T5 for entity serialization in combination with FAISS for indexing and searching the top-N candidate pairs per entity [21]. For the pre-trained LLMs, we used models provided by Ollama⁸, while for their fine-tuning we used Unsloth⁹. All of our code, datasets and fine-tuned models are publicly available¹⁰. All experiments were executed on a server with Ubuntu 20.04, AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3960X 24-Core processor, 256 GB RAM and an RTX 4090 GPU.

4.2 Candidate Generation

Strategy	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	Mean
Ranking@10	0.84	0.61	0.83	0.69	0.60	0.63	0.71	0.70	0.70
Rec. Pruning	0.87	0.59	0.86	0.74	0.64	0.67	0.72	0.76	0.73
Hybrid@4	0.47	0.41	0.84	0.88	0.64	0.82	0.30	0.75	0.64

Table 2: Comparison on F1 for different Post-Blocking Refinement approaches for SELECT prompts and using Llama-3.1 for inference.

In this experiment, we assess the effect of Post-Blocking Refinement on the performance of *AvengER*. We actually measure the evolution of Blocking effectiveness with regard to the Blocking parameter $k \in [1, 10]$ with a step of 1.

⁶ <https://ollama.com/library/{X}> llama3.1:8b, mistral:7b, orca2:7b, qwen2.5:32b

⁷ <https://huggingface.co/google/flan-t5-xl>

⁸ <https://ollama.com/>

⁹ <https://unsloth.ai/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/alexZeakis/AvengER>

We consider two variants of the *COS-ST5* strategy: “*Left-to-Right*” indexes the larger data source and queries with the entity descriptions of the smaller one, and vice versa for “*Right-to-Left*”. To be noted, the size of a data collection reflects the number of entities within it. For Filtering, we use Reciprocal Pruning.

As shown in Figure 9, Right-to-Left exhibits a relatively stable F1 score across all k in each dataset. The reason is that it consistently maintains high recall at the cost of lower precision. Left-to-Right starts from low F1 scores but raises above Right-to-Left in most cases for $k=10$. This should be attributed to a similar trend in recall, given that its precision is consistently very high. Reciprocal Pruning significantly outperforms the other two strategies with respect to both recall and precision across all k values, due to the consistently lower number of candidates for almost the same recall.

Our next step is to measure the effectiveness of Post-Blocking Refinement strategies in combination with Matching. We compare three different approaches: (i) For Ranking, we use *COS-ST5* with Left-to-Right and $k = 10$. (ii) For Filtering, we use Reciprocal Pruning with $k = 10$. (iii) For Hybrid, we set $k = 10, N = 4$ and use Flan-T5-XL, as in [18]. In all cases, we use the basic SELECT prompt and Llama-3.1 as a model. We omit Ranking with COMPARE prompts and Filtering with MATCH prompts, since preliminary results show no significant differences in terms of effectiveness, while the extra prompts yield a considerable overhead in terms of time efficiency. Besides, these strategies are partially covered by the Hybrid one.

As shown in Table 2, one-directional Blocking with $k = 10$ generally underperforms Reciprocal Pruning to a significant extent. The only exception is *D2*, where the duplicate pairs are so noisy that in many cases, one of them is more similar to non-matching entity descriptions. Reciprocal Pruning also outperforms Hybrid in datasets like *D1*, *D2*, and *D7*, because Hybrid struggles with the variability in product descriptions, but the latter performs better in movie-related datasets like *D4*, *D5*, and *D6*. Combined with the fact that Hybrid requires k prompts in an LLM, thus higher computational cost, Reciprocal Pruning offers a better balance of efficiency and performance.

Summary: On average, Reciprocal Pruning outperforms the other strategies, yielding a much higher F-Measure, while exhibiting the best and most stable balance between effectiveness and time efficiency.

4.3 Matching

Prompt Evaluation. We now study the performance of variants of the basic prompt, regarding the parts “in-context learning”, “serialization” and “task description”. For in-context learning, we extended the basic SELECT prompt with two examples. For serialization, we compare the schema-aware and schema-agnostic strategies with the summaries created by Llama-3.1. For Task Description, we study SELECT, EXPLAIN and CONFIDENCE prompts with Llama-3.1, Mistral-v0.3 and Orca-2. For each experiment, we use the Standard Blocking with Reciprocal Pruning for Candidate Generation, based on Section 4.2.

Task	Serialization	ICL	Model	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	Mean	RSize
SEL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Llama-3.1	0.87	0.59	0.86	<u>0.74</u>	<u>0.64</u>	<u>0.67</u>	0.72	0.76	0.73	107
(a) Baseline													
SEL.	Sch.-Aw.	FS	Llama-3.1	0.77	0.47	0.77	0.65	0.62	0.51	0.53	0.72	0.63	1011
(b) Few-shot variation													
SEL.	Summary	ZS	Llama-3.1	0.75	0.46	0.83	<u>0.74</u>	0.65	0.72	0.61	0.73	0.69	57
SEL.	Sch.-Agn.	ZS	Llama-3.1	<u>0.86</u>	<u>0.60</u>	0.88	0.73	0.61	<u>0.67</u>	0.69	<u>0.75</u>	<u>0.72</u>	13
(c) Zero-shot Variation of Serialization methods													
SEL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Mistral-v0.3	0.75	0.44	0.82	0.70	0.43	0.58	0.56	0.66	0.62	228
SEL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Orca-2	0.6	0.35	0.73	0.62	0.42	0.5	0.42	0.61	0.53	1879
EXPL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Llama-3.1	<u>0.86</u>	<u>0.60</u>	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.65	0.70	0.74	<u>0.72</u>	366
EXPL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Mistral-v0.3	0.83	0.56	0.81	0.68	0.56	0.60	0.69	0.64	0.67	480
EXPL.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Orca-2	0.54	0.31	0.75	0.5	0.34	0.48	0.34	0.61	0.48	1640
CONF.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Llama-3.1	0.84	0.61	0.86	0.75	0.65	<u>0.67</u>	<u>0.71</u>	<u>0.75</u>	0.73	198
CONF.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Mistral-v0.3	0.84	0.57	<u>0.87</u>	<u>0.74</u>	0.54	0.66	0.69	0.72	0.70	218
CONF.	Sch.-Aw.	ZS	Orca-2	0.54	0.27	0.70	0.5	0.39	0.45	0.30	0.64	0.47	1841
(d) Zero-shot Variation of Task Description methods and models													

Table 3: F1 per prompt variation. The rightmost column reports the average response size in characters. Note that ICL stands for in-context learning, RSize for Response Size, ZS for Zero-Shot prompts and FS for Few-Shot ones.

The results are reported in Table 3. For Llama-3.1, Zero-Shot prompts outperform Few-Shot prompts across all datasets, with an increase in average F-Measure from 0.63 to 0.73. This is likely due to SELECT prompts being sensitive to token count, where adding 2x more options significantly increases average response size from 107 to 1011 characters. This suggests that models can be disoriented by bigger prompts and hints potential improvements through better example selection.

Schema-agnostic serialization performs well with an average of 0.72, surpassing other techniques in D2 and D3 but ranking below the baseline, which uses Schema-Aware serialization. Its limitation lies in omitting predicates that are often semantically rich, particularly for datasets with distinctive predicates like titles or names.

Comparing Llama-3.1 with the other two LLMs, we observe that it consistently dominates them across all three types of prompts, i.e., SELECT, EXPLAIN and CONFIDENCE. The best performance of Mistral-v0.3 is achieved with CONFIDENCE prompts, which still underperform the baseline. Orca-2 consistently yields much lower F1 scores along with the longest responses.

Summary: Adding random examples in SELECT prompts can degrade performance for the 7B LLMs we are examining, while including predicates in entity serialization improves model accuracy but requires domain-specific knowledge for richer descriptions. Requiring explanations or confidence measures in prompts further can enhance performance for models that are weaker in reasoning.

Voting Evaluation. We now study the performance of the suggested voting strategies on pre-trained LLMs. The ensemble of models consists of Llama-3.1, Mistral-v0.3 and Orca-2. For Weighted-vote, we obtained the weights per model by normalizing F1 scores from inferencing EXPLAIN prompts on unseen data. For the Aggregated Majority-vote, each model was inferenced 5 times. For the

Task	Model	Vote	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	Mean	RSize
SEL.	Llama-3.1	Single	0.87	0.59	0.86	0.74	0.64	0.67	0.72	0.76	0.73	107
(a) Baseline												
SEL.	Ens.	Majority	0.86	0.57	0.90	0.77	0.65	0.71	0.71	0.78	0.74	738
SEL.	Ens.	Weighted	0.87	0.58	0.87	0.74	0.63	0.69	0.71	0.77	0.73	738
EXPL.	Llama-3.1	Single	0.86	0.60	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.65	0.70	0.74	0.72	366
EXPL.	Ens.	Majority	0.87	0.61	0.88	0.73	0.62	0.69	0.73	0.77	0.74	829
EXPL.	Ens.	Weighted	0.87	0.61	0.86	0.70	0.61	0.66	0.71	0.75	0.72	829
CONF.	Llama-3.1	Single	0.84	0.61	0.86	0.75	0.65	0.67	0.71	0.75	0.73	198
CONF.	Ens.	Majority	0.87	0.60	0.89	0.77	0.66	0.70	0.76	0.80	0.76	752
CONF.	Ens.	Weighted	0.86	0.61	0.87	0.74	0.63	0.66	0.73	0.75	0.73	752
(b) Internal Voting Techniques												
CONF.	Ens.	Conf.	0.87	0.60	0.89	0.77	0.66	0.71	0.76	0.80	0.76	752
EXPL.	Ens.	Agg.Majority	0.90	0.63	0.90	0.74	0.64	0.75	0.78	0.80	0.77	818
(c) Internal Confidence Voting Techniques												
EXPL.	Ens.	Judge-Llama-3.1	0.82	0.58	0.87	0.75	0.64	0.65	0.65	0.75	0.71	107
EXPL.	Ens.	Judge-Qwen-2.5	0.93	0.62	0.93	0.81	0.69	0.69	0.50	0.86	0.75	443
EXPL.	Ens.	Hybrid- $\theta=0.6$	0.93	0.66	0.91	0.77	0.67	0.77	0.82	0.85	0.80	818
(d) External Voting Techniques												

Table 4: Comparison on F1 for different internal and external voting strategies on the ensemble of models. RSize stands for Response Size.

Judge-vote, we utilized the responses of the EXPLAIN prompts of the ensemble and used two model as judges: Llama-3.1 and Qwen-2.5. Note, though, that due to the higher resource requirements of Qwen-2.5, it was not possible to process all prompts. Finally, for the Hybrid-vote, we used Aggregated Majority-vote as the internal vote and Qwen-2.5 as the external judge. To examine voting complementarity, we also consider the “*Any-vote*” strategy, where any pair marked as match from any strategy is treated as a match.

We start by assessing the complementarity between pre-trained models, i.e., whether a model X can find pairs that a model Y cannot find. To do so, we use as baseline the performance of Llama-3.1 with EXPLAIN prompts and compare it with Majority-vote and Any-vote. Any-vote has the highest Recall at 0.87, while Majority-vote and the baseline reach 0.76 and 0.80, respectively. This suggests that the three models of the ensemble are indeed complementary. However, the increased number of false positives produced by Any-vote significantly lowers its Precision and F-Measure to 0.49 and 0.62, respectively. In contrast, Majority-vote sacrifices some Recall compared to the baseline but improves Precision (0.72), leading to a better overall F1 score (0.74).

After verifying the complementarity of the voting schemes, we compare the performance of the internal ones in more detail in Table 4. We observe that Majority-vote consistently outperforms the baseline across all prompt types, with a larger difference for CONFIDENCE prompts, where it averages 0.76 compared to 0.73. Weighted-vote performs similarly to the baseline, with the weight assigned to Llama-3.1 dominating the other two LLMs. Confidence-vote in Table 4(c) performs at least as good as the Majority-vote with CONFIDENCE prompts. In fact, the Aggregated Majority-vote achieves the highest average F1 score among all internal voting schemes at 0.77, exhibiting the best performance in most datasets, but requires significantly more model executions than Majority-vote.

Fig. 3: Hybrid Voting strategy performance with various thresholds θ .

Regarding the external voting techniques in Table 4(d), between the two models used as Judge, Qwen-2.5 outperforms Llama-3.1 on most datasets. This highlights the advantages of Qwen-2.5’s larger size, enabling better contextual understanding and handling of complex relationships. On the downside, Qwen-2.5 has high memory requirements, which forced us to restrict its input size in datasets with long entity descriptions. Hence its poor performance in D7.

Finally, the Hybrid-vote method balances internal and external strategies so well that it outperforms all other ensembles on average, ranking first or second in all datasets. Figure 3 depicts its fine-tuning with respect to θ . Its best performance corresponds to $\theta = 0.6$, where it utilizes Judge decisions only 12% of the time. This performance reflects the complementary nature of internal and external strategies and the flexibility of the Hybrid one in combining them.

Summary: Models can be complementary to each other, thus calling for an ensemble of LLMs. Using the hybrid voting strategy is both effective and efficient.

Model	Type	Vote	PB Ref.	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	Mean	RSize
Llama-3.1	PT	Single	Rec.	0.86	0.60	0.85	0.71	0.61	0.65	0.70	0.74	0.72	366
Mistral-v0.3	PT	Single	Rec.	0.83	0.56	0.81	0.68	0.56	0.60	0.69	0.64	0.67	480
(a) Pre-Trained Models													
Llama-3.1	FT	Single	Rec.	<u>0.94</u>	0.66	<u>0.98</u>	<u>0.89</u>	0.8	0.90	<u>0.89</u>	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.88</u>	115
Llama-3.1-ins.	FT	Single	Rec.	<u>0.94</u>	0.69	<u>0.98</u>	0.90	0.78	0.90	<u>0.89</u>	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.88</u>	3
Mistral-v0.3	FT	Single	Rec.	<u>0.94</u>	0.69	<u>0.98</u>	0.90	0.78	0.92	<u>0.88</u>	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.88</u>	3
Mistral-v0.3-ins.	FT	Single	Rec.	<u>0.94</u>	0.68	0.99	0.90	<u>0.79</u>	0.90	<u>0.89</u>	<u>0.96</u>	<u>0.88</u>	3
(b) Fine-Tuned Models													
Mistral-v0.3-ins.	FT	Single	Rank@10	<u>0.94</u>	0.70	<u>0.98</u>	0.90	0.77	0.90	<u>0.89</u>	<u>0.96</u>	<u>0.88</u>	3
(c) Fine-Tuned with no Post-Blocking Refinement													
Ensemble-FT	FT	Majority	Rec.	0.95	0.69	0.97	<u>0.89</u>	<u>0.79</u>	<u>0.91</u>	<u>0.89</u>	0.95	<u>0.88</u>	31
Ensemble-FT	FT	Any	Rec.	0.93	0.68	0.97	<u>0.89</u>	0.77	0.89	0.87	0.94	0.87	31
(d) Complementarity of Fine-Tuned models.													

Table 5: Comparison on F1 for different individual and ensemble of fine-tuned models. PB Ref. stands for Post-Blocking Refinement, Rec. for Reciprocal Pruning, PT for Pre-Trained, FT for Fine-Tuned and RSize for Response Size.

PB Ref.	Task	Model	Type	Vote	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	Mean
Rec.	EXPL.	Ensemble	PT	Hyb- $\theta=0.6$	0.93	0.66	0.91	0.77	0.67	0.77	0.82	0.85	0.80
Rec.	EXPL.	Mistral-v0.3-Ins.	FT	Single	0.94	0.68	0.99	0.90	0.79	0.90	0.89	0.96	0.88
Hyb@4	SEL.	GPT-3.5	PT	Single	0.88	0.70	0.91	0.97	0.84	0.85	0.86	0.85	0.86
Ran@10	SEL	Mistral-v0.1-Ins.	PT	Single	0.67	0.57	0.83	0.74	0.88	0.77	0.81	0.63	0.74

Table 6: F1 per baseline and best Supervised and Unsupervised method. Rec. stands for Reciprocal Pruning, Hyb. for Hybrid, Ran for Ranking.

Fine-Tuning Evaluation. In this experiment, we evaluate the performance of fine-tuned LLMs with that of their pre-trained version, examining how fine-tuning affects the complementarity of the models and their sensitivity to position bias. We fine-tune Llama-3.1 and Mistral-v0.3, excluding Orca, due to its low performance. For both models, we used the base and instruct variations.

The results are reported in Table 5. For Llama-3.1, the fine-tuned versions consistently outperform the pre-trained model by 24% on average (the average F1 score raises from 0.72 to 0.88). For Mistral, the improvement is even more significant, raising to 31%: while the pre-trained model averages 0.67, both fine-tuned variants reach 0.88, matching the F1 of the fine-tuned Llama-3.1 models. All four models show Precision=0.89 and Recall=0.87 on average.

Regarding the complementarity of the fine-tuned models, we assess it by comparing Any-vote with Majority-vote in Table 5(d). Unlike their pre-trained models, the two voting strategies achieve similarly high levels of Recall and F1, thus indicating low levels of complementarity.

Regarding the sensitivity to position bias of fine-tuned models, we compare Llama-3.1 (the best pre-trained LLM) with Mistral-v0.3-instruct (the best fine-tuned LLM) across 10 EXPLAIN prompt permutations per dataset, where the positions of the candidates were randomly shuffled. The results in Figures 8 (a) and (b) show that the F1 score of the fine-tuned model exhibits significantly lower variance, on average across all datasets (0.0061 vs. 0.0116 for pre-trained). We executed the same experiment for the fine-tuned Llama-3.1 and it showed the same behavior, with an average variance of 0.0069. This indicates that fine-tuning allows for learning to handle prompt variations effectively. To further verify that fine-tuning mitigates position bias, we conducted an additional experiment using prompts with the original $k = 10$ Blocking choices, with results shown in Table 5(c). The fine-tuned model maintains consistent performance across datasets, unlike pre-trained models, as shown in Table 2. These findings confirm that fine-tuning reduces position bias, enabling prompts with more options without sacrificing accuracy.

Summary: A medium-sized fine-tuned model achieves up to a 31% higher F1 score compared to its pre-trained version, showing low complementarity to other fine-tuned models and lower sensitivity to position bias.

4.4 Comparison with Baselines

This experiment compares our methods to two established baselines from the literature, ComEM [18]. Specifically, we used the best of their methods, which

was the Hybrid@4 Post-Blocking Strategy combined with a pre-trained GPT-3.5 and we also used the Ranking@10 with a pre-trained Mistral-v0.1-Instruct:7b, which is also comparable to our own. For our methods, for unsupervised settings we consider the Hybrid voting using Qwen-2.5 as an external Judge and the Aggregated-Majority as an internal voting strategy on the ensemble of pre-trained models. For the supervised settings, we consider the fine-tuned Mistral-v0.3-Instruct. The results are reported in Table 6.

Our unsupervised approach dominates the Mistral baseline almost always, with the exception of D5, but significantly underperforms the GPT baseline in all datasets. This can be explained by the vast difference between medium-size models and the large-size GPT-3.5, which can handle many tasks effectively without further training. However, our ensemble of models is more cost-effective, given that GPT-3.5 constitutes a proprietary model that is billable and requires a considerable budget to operate.

The situation is reversed under the supervised settings. The fine-tuned Mistral is superior to the baseline algorithm in most datasets, yielding an average F1 of 0.88. This demonstrates that in the case of annotated data, we can fine-tune an open-source model to even surpass a large-size model.

Summary: An ensemble of open-source medium-size models offers a cost-effective alternative to a proprietary large model in unsupervised settings, while fine-tuning a medium-size model can achieve better performance than a large pre-trained model.

5 Conclusions

We introduced *AvengER* to effectively handle both unsupervised and supervised settings. First, we demonstrated that reducing prompt options is crucial for select prompts and proposed Reciprocal Pruning as a means of significantly reducing the candidate pairs generated by Blocking. We showed that serialization with predicates is also crucial, and random examples should be avoided in In-Context Learning. Instead, advanced example selection techniques are required. We also examined ensembles of LLMs, showing that the individual models typically yield complementary results. Internal voting conveys minor improvements in effectiveness, while external voting is resource-intensive, due to the larger model that lies at its core. Our hybrid voting strategy nicely balances these two voting strategies, matching the external voting’s performance by calling the Judge model for just 12% of the prompts. This approach suits low-resource settings. In applications with labelled data, Fine-Tuning is a stronger alternative, as it demonstrates robustness, effectively mitigates position bias, and enables medium-sized models to surpass large pre-trained ones.

Acknowledgements

This work was partially funded by the EU project STELAR (Horizon Europe – Grant No. 101070122).

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Fig. 4: Post-Blocking Strategies.

Select a record from the following candidates that refers to the same real-world entity as the given record. Answer with the corresponding record number surrounded by "[]" or "[0]" if there is none and explain briefly why.

Given entity record: [COL] name [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H [COL] description [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H/ Belt Drive System/ 33-1/3 and 45 RPM Speeds/ Servo Speed Control/ Supplied Moving Magnet Phono Cartridge/ Bonded Diamond Stylus/ Static Balance Tonearm/ Pitch Control

Candidate records:

[1] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-29F Analog Record Turntable - DP29F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive
 [2] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PS-LX350H Belt-Drive Turntable
 [3] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PSLX300USB USB Record Turntable [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 119.72
 [4] [COL] name [VAL] Sony Picture Station Digital Photo Printer - DPPFP95
 [5] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-300F Analog Record Turntable - DP300F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 328.99

LLM Response: [2] The candidate record [2] refers to the same real-world entity as the given record, specifically a Sony turntable model (PS-LX350H). The names and descriptions in both records match exactly.

EXPLAIN Prompt

Fig. 5: Prompt for EXPLAIN.

Select a record from the following candidates that refers to the same real-world entity as the given record. Answer with the corresponding record number surrounded by "[]" or "[0]" if there is none. Accompany your answer by one of the following confidence measures: {Certain},{Moderately-certain}, {Uncertain}.

Given entity record: [COL] name [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H [COL] description [VAL] Sony Turntable - PSLX350H/ Belt Drive System/ 33-1/3 and 45 RPM Speeds/ Servo Speed Control/ Supplied Moving Magnet Phono Cartridge/ Bonded Diamond Stylus/ Static Balance Tonearm/ Pitch Control

Candidate records:

[1] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-29F Analog Record Turntable - DP29F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive
 [2] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PS-LX350H Belt-Drive Turntable
 [3] [COL] name [VAL] Sony PSLX300USB USB Record Turntable [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 119.72
 [4] [COL] name [VAL] Sony Picture Station Digital Photo Printer - DPPFP95
 [5] [COL] name [VAL] Denon DP-300F Analog Record Turntable - DP300F [COL] description [VAL] Belt Drive [COL] price [VAL] 328.99

LLM Response: [Certain] [2] The given entity record refers to a Sony turntable model, and candidate record [2] is the exact match for this real-world entity.

CONFIDENCE Prompt

Fig. 6: Prompt for CONFIDENCE.

Appendix

Fine-Tuning Configuration: For the training data described in Section 4.1, we used zero-shot SELECT prompts with schema-aware serialization and provided

Fig. 7: Prompts for creating a Summary for dataset description.

Fig. 8: Measuring variance in performance for permuted prompts between the best of pre-trained and fine-tuned models

Fig. 9: Comparing Post-Blocking Refinement strategies for different values of k .

the answer in brackets. For each entity we created 3 such prompts, with the answers shuffled, to cover the issue of position bias. For training, we used LoRA with rank 16, $\alpha = 16$, and no dropout for efficient adaptation while managing memory constraints. Training was conducted for three epochs with a learning rate of $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$, gradient accumulation steps of 4, and the AdamW 8-bit optimizer. To reduce memory usage, we applied 4-bit quantization to non-instruction-tuned models.